

Cambridge Centre for Proteomics Mascot Search Results

User : anja
Email : aa2030@cam.ac.uk
Search title : P378 (\\prot-filesvr1\data\CORE\PARAMETERS\Mascot_search_parameters\Yagnesh\M291_Ben_Luisi_tolc_arca_velos_xlink_ox_chymo_041218.par), submitted from Daemon on CCP-PC158
MS data file : \\prot-filesvr1\data\CORE\RAW_DATA_2018_Velos\P378_Ben_Luisi\P378_Band_2_BSA_control.mgf
Database 1 : cRAP 20181217 (120 sequences; 39582 residues)
Database 2 : M291_ARCA ARCA_20181203 (1 sequences; 238 residues)
Database 3 : M291_TOLC TOLC_20181203 (1 sequences; 493 residues)
Timestamp : 19 Dec 2018 at 09:57:40 GMT

Protein hits : [1::sp|cRAP087|P02769|ALBU BOVIN](#) Serum albumin OS=Bos taurus GN=ALB PE=1
[1::sp|cRAP002|P02768|ALBU HUMAN](#) Serum albumin OS=Homo sapiens GN=ALB PE=1
[1::sp|cRAP022|P00766|CTRA BOVIN](#) Chymotrypsinogen A OS=Bos taurus PE=1 SV=1
[1::sp|cRAP112|P00761|TRYP PIG](#) Trypsin OS=Sus scrofa PE=1 SV=1
[1::sp|cRAP091|Q10735|PEPB PIG](#) Pepsin B (Fragment) OS=Sus scrofa GN=PGB
[1::sp|cRAP015|P02666|CASB BOVIN](#) Beta-casein OS=Bos taurus GN=CSN2 PE=1 SV=1
[1::sp|cRAP008|P00722|BGAL ECOLI](#) Beta-galactosidase OS=Escherichia coli (GN=ECOL) PE=1 SV=1
[1::sp|cRAP004|P04745|AMY1 HUMAN](#) Alpha-amylase 1 OS=Homo sapiens GN=AMY1A PE=1 SV=1
[1::sp|cRAP020|P01031|CO5 HUMAN](#) Complement C5 OS=Homo sapiens GN=C5 PE=1 SV=1

Mascot Score Histogram

Ions score is $-10 \cdot \log(P)$, where P is the probability that the observed match is a random event. Individual ions scores > 15 indicate identity or extensive homology ($p < 0.05$). Protein scores are derived from ions scores as a non-probabilistic basis for ranking protein hits.

Peptide Summary Report

Protein Family Summary	Peptide Summary	Select Summary (protein hits)	Select Summary (unassigned)	Exp
Significance threshold p<				
Standard scoring MudPIT scoring				
Show pop-ups Suppress pop-ups				
Preferred taxonomy All entries .. Archaea (Archaeobacteria) .. Eukaryota (eucaryotes) Alveolata (alveo and relatives) bony vertebrates lobe-finned fish and tetrapod clade Mam Mus. Mus musculus (house mouse) Rattus Oth fishes) Takifugu rubripes (Japanese Pufferfish) Danio rerio (zebra fish) Schizosaccharomyces pombe (fission yeast) Pneumocystis carinii Other Fungi Viridiplant Mycobacterium tuberculosis complex Other Actinobacteria (class) Firmicutes (gram-positive bac Agrobacterium tumefaciens Campylobacter jejuni Escherichia coli Neisseria meningit Species information unavailable				

Error tolerant

- [1::sp|cRAP087|P02769|ALBU BOVIN](#) **Mass:** 71244 **Score:** 2258 **Matches:** 343 (343) S
 Serum albumin OS=Bos taurus GN=ALB PE=1 SV=4
 Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Pepti
256	396.6888	791.3630	791.3636	-0.77	1	(23)	0.0056	1		Y.LQQ
260	396.6890	791.3635	791.3636	-0.14	1	24	0.0043	1		Y.LQQ
383	404.6949	807.3752	807.3763	-1.29	0	(30)	0.0011	1	U	Y.QEA
385	404.6951	807.3757	807.3763	-0.69	0	(35)	0.0003	1	U	Y.QEA
388	404.6952	807.3758	807.3763	-0.62	0	(39)	0.00013	1	U	Y.QEA
391	404.6954	807.3762	807.3763	-0.10	0	(39)	0.00014	1	U	Y.QEA
392	404.6955	807.3764	807.3763	0.23	0	41	8.6e-05	1	U	Y.QEA

410	405.2235	808.4324	808.4331	-0.83	1	(25)	0.0033	1	U	Y.STV
411	405.2237	808.4328	808.4331	-0.38	1	28	0.0015	1	U	Y.STV
806	426.2105	850.4065	850.4072	-0.84	1	(22)	0.0084	1	U	L.VNE
807	426.2107	850.4068	850.4072	-0.56	1	(38)	0.0002	1	U	L.VNE
808	426.2107	850.4068	850.4072	-0.56	1	(23)	0.0064	1	U	L.VNE
809	426.2107	850.4068	850.4072	-0.56	1	(21)	0.0087	1	U	L.VNE
810	426.2107	850.4068	850.4072	-0.49	1	(24)	0.0044	1	U	L.VNE
811	426.2108	850.4069	850.4072	-0.35	1	(24)	0.0043	1	U	L.VNE
814	426.2110	850.4074	850.4072	0.24	1	(20)	0.012	1	U	L.VNE
815	426.2111	850.4076	850.4072	0.45	1	(32)	0.0007	1	U	L.VNE
817	426.2111	850.4077	850.4072	0.52	1	(35)	0.00039	1	U	L.VNE
818	426.2112	850.4078	850.4072	0.67	1	(34)	0.00044	1	U	L.VNE
819	426.2112	850.4079	850.4072	0.74	1	45	3.4e-05	1	U	L.VNE
821	426.2135	850.4125	850.4072	6.19	1	(36)	0.00027	1	U	L.VNE
948	434.7153	867.4160	867.4160	-0.05	0	(31)	0.00085	1	U	L.KTV
949	434.7153	867.4160	867.4160	-0.05	0	(21)	0.0073	1	U	L.KTV
950	434.7154	867.4163	867.4160	0.37	0	43	4.9e-05	1	U	L.KTV
951	434.7157	867.4168	867.4160	0.87	0	(43)	5.3e-05	1	U	L.KTV
1056	442.7124	883.4103	883.4109	-0.73	0	(23)	0.0049	1	U	L.KTV
1057	442.7131	883.4116	883.4109	0.79	0	(25)	0.003	1	U	L.KTV
1281	457.2244	912.4342	912.4341	0.15	1	47	2.2e-05	1	U	Y.ANK
1282	457.2251	912.4356	912.4341	1.68	1	(40)	0.0001	1	U	Y.ANK
1340	461.2375	920.4604	920.4603	0.04	1	25	0.0031	1	U	Y.QEA
1345	461.2376	920.4607	920.4603	0.44	1	(24)	0.0041	1	U	Y.QEA
1348	461.2381	920.4616	920.4603	1.44	1	(23)	0.0049	1	U	Y.QEA
1349	461.2381	920.4616	920.4603	1.44	1	(24)	0.0039	1	U	Y.QEA
1363	461.7288	921.4430	921.4443	-1.48	1	(22)	0.0057	1	U	Y.QEA
1510	472.7388	943.4630	943.4624	0.70	0	22	0.0063	1	U	Y.SRR
1769	487.7304	973.4463	973.4505	-4.35	1	(31)	0.00088	1	U	F.KDL
1771	487.7310	973.4474	973.4505	-3.16	1	(28)	0.002	1	U	F.KDL
1772	487.7318	973.4491	973.4505	-1.47	1	(40)	0.00011	1	U	F.KDL
1773	487.7318	973.4491	973.4505	-1.47	1	(30)	0.0013	1	U	F.KDL
1774	487.7320	973.4494	973.4505	-1.10	1	(27)	0.002	1	U	F.KDL
1775	487.7321	973.4496	973.4505	-0.90	1	(34)	0.00043	1	U	F.KDL
1776	487.7321	973.4497	973.4505	-0.83	1	(27)	0.0022	1	U	F.KDL
1777	487.7322	973.4499	973.4505	-0.59	1	(49)	1.3e-05	1	U	F.KDL
1778	487.7323	973.4500	973.4505	-0.53	1	(35)	0.00032	1	U	F.KDL
1779	487.7323	973.4500	973.4505	-0.53	1	(29)	0.0014	1	U	F.KDL
1780	487.7323	973.4501	973.4505	-0.40	1	(28)	0.0018	1	U	F.KDL
1781	487.7326	973.4506	973.4505	0.09	1	(31)	0.00087	1	U	F.KDL
1782	487.7326	973.4506	973.4505	0.09	1	(33)	0.00055	1	U	F.KDL
1783	487.7326	973.4507	973.4505	0.23	1	(27)	0.002	1	U	F.KDL
1784	487.7326	973.4507	973.4505	0.23	1	(33)	0.00049	1	U	F.KDL
1785	487.7326	973.4507	973.4505	0.23	1	(37)	0.00022	1	U	F.KDL
1786	487.7327	973.4508	973.4505	0.30	1	(31)	0.00079	1	U	F.KDL
1787	487.7327	973.4509	973.4505	0.42	1	(32)	0.00065	1	U	F.KDL
1788	487.7328	973.4510	973.4505	0.48	1	(38)	0.00017	1	U	F.KDL
1789	487.7328	973.4510	973.4505	0.54	1	(32)	0.00067	1	U	F.KDL
1790	487.7328	973.4511	973.4505	0.60	1	(29)	0.0013	1	U	F.KDL
1791	487.7329	973.4513	973.4505	0.79	1	(38)	0.00018	1	U	F.KDL
1792	487.7329	973.4513	973.4505	0.79	1	(30)	0.00095	1	U	F.KDL
1793	487.7329	973.4513	973.4505	0.85	1	(49)	1.3e-05	1	U	F.KDL
1794	487.7329	973.4513	973.4505	0.85	1	(42)	7.4e-05	1	U	F.KDL
1795	487.7329	973.4513	973.4505	0.85	1	(35)	0.00034	1	U	F.KDL
1796	487.7330	973.4514	973.4505	0.91	1	(28)	0.0018	1	U	F.KDL
1797	487.7330	973.4515	973.4505	1.04	1	(34)	0.00038	1	U	F.KDL
1798	487.7330	973.4515	973.4505	1.04	1	(27)	0.0021	1	U	F.KDL

1799	487.7332	973.4518	973.4505	1.34	1	53	5.4e-06	1	U	F.KDL
1800	487.7337	973.4528	973.4505	2.41	1	(30)	0.0012	1	U	F.KDL
1801	487.7337	973.4528	973.4505	2.41	1	(23)	0.0048	1	U	F.KDL
1802	487.7348	973.4550	973.4505	4.67	1	(25)	0.0031	1	U	F.KDL
2004	498.7301	995.4456	995.4447	0.84	1	(37)	0.00019	1	U	F.SAL
2005	498.7302	995.4458	995.4447	1.02	1	(32)	0.00067	1	U	F.SAL
2006	498.7303	995.4460	995.4447	1.23	1	53	5e-06	1	U	F.SAL
2007	498.7304	995.4462	995.4447	1.47	1	(30)	0.00096	1	U	F.SAL
2417	521.2842	1040.5538	1040.5515	2.19	0	25	0.0032	1		Y.EIA
2499	526.2817	1050.5489	1050.5498	-0.83	1	39	0.00012	1	U	F.KAD
2500	526.2827	1050.5509	1050.5498	1.01	1	(34)	0.00038	1	U	F.KAD
2515	526.7383	1051.4620	1051.4757	-12.96	0	(28)	0.0026	1	U	L.IKQ
2518	526.7451	1051.4756	1051.4757	-0.10	0	(24)	0.0074	1	U	L.IKQ
2519	526.7452	1051.4758	1051.4757	0.12	0	(26)	0.0047	1	U	L.IKQ
2520	526.7452	1051.4758	1051.4757	0.12	0	(31)	0.0013	1	U	L.IKQ
2521	526.7452	1051.4758	1051.4757	0.12	0	(35)	0.00059	1	U	L.IKQ
2522	526.7452	1051.4758	1051.4757	0.12	0	(30)	0.0017	1	U	L.IKQ
2523	526.7452	1051.4758	1051.4757	0.12	0	(28)	0.0026	1	U	L.IKQ
2524	526.7452	1051.4758	1051.4757	0.12	0	(25)	0.0054	1	U	L.IKQ
2525	526.7456	1051.4767	1051.4757	0.94	0	(24)	0.0076	1	U	L.IKQ
2526	526.7457	1051.4769	1051.4757	1.17	0	(34)	0.00077	1	U	L.IKQ
2527	526.7457	1051.4769	1051.4757	1.17	0	(29)	0.0023	1	U	L.IKQ
2528	526.7457	1051.4769	1051.4757	1.17	0	(21)	0.015	1	U	L.IKQ
2530	526.7459	1051.4771	1051.4757	1.40	0	58	2.6e-06	1	U	L.IKQ
2531	526.7460	1051.4775	1051.4757	1.74	0	(33)	0.00086	1	U	L.IKQ
2532	526.7460	1051.4775	1051.4757	1.74	0	(47)	3.5e-05	1	U	L.IKQ
2534	526.7462	1051.4779	1051.4757	2.10	0	(31)	0.0017	1	U	L.IKQ
2535	526.7465	1051.4785	1051.4757	2.67	0	(23)	0.01	1	U	L.IKQ
2536	526.7466	1051.4786	1051.4757	2.79	0	(21)	0.015	1	U	L.IKQ
2539	527.2316	1052.4487	1052.4597	-10.43	0	(32)	0.00083	1	U	L.IKQ
2540	527.2323	1052.4500	1052.4597	-9.16	0	(22)	0.0079	1	U	L.IKQ
2612	531.7418	1061.4690	1061.4488	19.0	1	(28)	0.0018	1	U	F.KDL
2621	532.7172	1063.4198	1063.4240	-4.00	0	(22)	0.0058	1		L.ECA
2623	532.7201	1063.4256	1063.4240	1.51	0	(39)	0.00011	1		L.ECA
2625	532.7202	1063.4259	1063.4240	1.73	0	43	4.7e-05	1		L.ECA
2627	532.7210	1063.4273	1063.4240	3.12	0	(28)	0.0015	1		L.ECA
2736	538.7567	1075.4989	1075.4974	1.33	2	30	0.001	1	U	Y.YAN
2737	538.7574	1075.5002	1075.4974	2.60	2	(26)	0.0024	1	U	Y.YAN
2741	539.2475	1076.4804	1076.4814	-0.93	2	(22)	0.0062	1	U	Y.YAN
2770	541.2874	1080.5603	1080.5604	-0.10	0	(25)	0.0031	1	U	L.SQK
2771	541.2877	1080.5609	1080.5604	0.47	0	(23)	0.0045	1	U	L.SQK
2773	541.2882	1080.5619	1080.5604	1.38	0	45	2.9e-05	1	U	L.SQK
2774	541.2882	1080.5619	1080.5604	1.38	0	(37)	0.00022	1	U	L.SQK
2785	541.7767	1081.5389	1081.5444	-5.07	0	(32)	0.00067	1	U	L.SQK
2786	541.7770	1081.5394	1081.5444	-4.60	0	(30)	0.00091	1	U	L.SQK
3029	558.8302	1115.6458	1115.6438	1.84	1	29	0.0012	1	U	F.VEV
3523	589.2612	1176.5078	1176.5081	-0.25	1	(40)	0.00011	1		L.LEC
3526	589.2626	1176.5106	1176.5081	2.13	1	45	3e-05	1		L.LEC
3565	590.8270	1179.6395	1179.6400	-0.44	2	(43)	4.9e-05	1	U	Y.GFQ
3566	590.8271	1179.6397	1179.6400	-0.24	2	(42)	5.8e-05	1	U	Y.GFQ
3570	591.3197	1180.6248	1180.6240	0.69	2	(42)	5.8e-05	1	U	Y.GFQ
3571	591.3202	1180.6259	1180.6240	1.62	2	(33)	0.00048	1	U	Y.GFQ
3572	591.3207	1180.6269	1180.6240	2.45	2	44	3.9e-05	1	U	Y.GFQ
3604	593.7941	1185.5737	1185.5740	-0.24	1	26	0.0026	1	U	L.KTV
3605	593.7946	1185.5746	1185.5740	0.49	1	(22)	0.0074	1	U	L.KTV
3656	596.8183	1191.6220	1191.6248	-2.29	1	(22)	0.0066	1	U	L.KHL
3661	596.8190	1191.6234	1191.6248	-1.16	1	(27)	0.0019	1	U	L.KHL

<u>3665</u>	596.8191	1191.6236	1191.6248	-0.96	1	(40)	0.0001	1	U	L.KHL
<u>3666</u>	596.8192	1191.6239	1191.6248	-0.76	1	42	7.1e-05	1	U	L.KHL
<u>3668</u>	596.8194	1191.6242	1191.6248	-0.44	1	(23)	0.0046	1	U	L.KHL
<u>3673</u>	596.8198	1191.6251	1191.6248	0.27	1	(24)	0.0045	1	U	L.KHL
<u>3675</u>	398.2158	1191.6255	1191.6248	0.65	1	(27)	0.0018	1	U	L.KHL
<u>3678</u>	596.8204	1191.6263	1191.6248	1.29	1	(20)	0.009	1	U	L.KHL
<u>3683</u>	596.8210	1191.6274	1191.6248	2.21	1	(22)	0.0063	1	U	L.KHL
<u>3696</u>	597.3111	1192.6076	1192.6088	-0.95	1	(34)	0.00041	1	U	L.KHL
<u>3698</u>	597.3112	1192.6079	1192.6088	-0.75	1	(27)	0.002	1	U	L.KHL
<u>3701</u>	398.5570	1192.6493	1192.6492	0.08	2	(29)	0.0011	1	U	Y.VPK
<u>3703</u>	398.5573	1192.6500	1192.6492	0.68	2	(26)	0.0025	1	U	Y.VPK
<u>3704</u>	597.3323	1192.6501	1192.6492	0.78	2	(36)	0.00027	1	U	Y.VPK
<u>3707</u>	597.3333	1192.6519	1192.6492	2.30	2	(32)	0.00061	1	U	Y.VPK
<u>3709</u>	597.3334	1192.6522	1192.6492	2.51	2	(36)	0.00023	1	U	Y.VPK
<u>3712</u>	597.3337	1192.6528	1192.6492	3.03	2	(27)	0.0021	1	U	Y.VPK
<u>3713</u>	597.3339	1192.6532	1192.6492	3.33	2	41	8.8e-05	1	U	Y.VPK
<u>3715</u>	597.3377	1192.6609	1192.6492	9.78	2	(38)	0.00017	1	U	Y.VPK
<u>4067</u>	613.8136	1225.6126	1225.6125	0.13	1	30	0.001	1	U	L.CKV
<u>4071</u>	613.8146	1225.6146	1225.6125	1.73	1	(24)	0.004	1	U	L.CKV
<u>4258</u>	414.5200	1240.5382	1240.5394	-0.93	0	(27)	0.0021	1	U	F.AED
<u>4259</u>	414.5201	1240.5386	1240.5394	-0.64	0	(30)	0.0012	1	U	F.AED
<u>4260</u>	621.2769	1240.5392	1240.5394	-0.17	0	(28)	0.0018	1	U	F.AED
<u>4261</u>	621.2772	1240.5399	1240.5394	0.41	0	30	0.0012	1	U	F.AED
<u>4623</u>	641.3429	1280.6712	1280.6475	18.6	2	(28)	0.0017	1	U	Y.VPK
<u>4847</u>	436.9144	1307.7214	1307.7197	1.27	0	(22)	0.0059	1	U	L.KHK
<u>4848</u>	654.8683	1307.7221	1307.7197	1.86	0	(33)	0.00048	1	U	L.KHK
<u>4849</u>	654.8689	1307.7232	1307.7197	2.70	0	47	1.8e-05	1	U	L.KHK
<u>4850</u>	654.8689	1307.7232	1307.7197	2.70	0	(30)	0.001	1	U	L.KHK
<u>4851</u>	654.8689	1307.7232	1307.7197	2.70	0	(35)	0.00029	1	U	L.KHK
<u>4852</u>	654.8692	1307.7238	1307.7197	3.16	0	(22)	0.0063	1	U	L.KHK
<u>4853</u>	654.8695	1307.7245	1307.7197	3.64	0	(40)	0.0001	1	U	L.KHK
<u>4962</u>	663.8903	1325.7660	1325.7667	-0.56	0	(35)	0.00035	1	U	Y.TRK
<u>4967</u>	663.8917	1325.7689	1325.7667	1.64	0	43	4.6e-05	1	U	Y.TRK
<u>5010</u>	668.2993	1334.5841	1334.5813	2.11	1	(28)	0.0014	1	U	L.KPD
<u>5011</u>	668.3003	1334.5861	1334.5813	3.66	1	31	0.00083	1	U	L.KPD
<u>5113</u>	451.2329	1350.6770	1350.6779	-0.70	0	(44)	5.5e-05	1	U	L.SHK
<u>5119</u>	451.2334	1350.6784	1350.6779	0.33	0	50	1.2e-05	1	U	L.SHK
<u>5375</u>	697.3327	1392.6508	1392.6555	-3.33	0	(60)	1.1e-06	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>5376</u>	697.3331	1392.6516	1392.6555	-2.80	0	(47)	2.3e-05	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>5377</u>	697.3334	1392.6522	1392.6555	-2.37	0	(46)	2.9e-05	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>5378</u>	697.3334	1392.6522	1392.6555	-2.37	0	(60)	1.1e-06	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>5379</u>	697.3334	1392.6523	1392.6555	-2.27	0	(63)	5.4e-07	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>5380</u>	697.3345	1392.6544	1392.6555	-0.79	0	(58)	1.8e-06	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>5381</u>	697.3345	1392.6545	1392.6555	-0.70	0	(66)	3.3e-07	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>5382</u>	697.3348	1392.6550	1392.6555	-0.34	0	(46)	2.9e-05	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>5383</u>	697.3348	1392.6551	1392.6555	-0.26	0	(43)	6.5e-05	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>5384</u>	697.3349	1392.6552	1392.6555	-0.17	0	(56)	3.1e-06	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>5385</u>	697.3350	1392.6554	1392.6555	-0.09	0	(57)	2.5e-06	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>5386</u>	697.3350	1392.6555	1392.6555	0.00	0	(58)	2e-06	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>5387</u>	697.3351	1392.6556	1392.6555	0.09	0	(72)	7.4e-08	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>5388</u>	697.3351	1392.6556	1392.6555	0.09	0	(59)	1.4e-06	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>5389</u>	697.3351	1392.6557	1392.6555	0.17	0	(73)	6.2e-08	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>5390</u>	697.3351	1392.6557	1392.6555	0.17	0	(64)	5.3e-07	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>5391</u>	697.3351	1392.6557	1392.6555	0.17	0	(37)	0.00022	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>5392</u>	697.3352	1392.6559	1392.6555	0.27	0	(66)	3e-07	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>5393</u>	697.3354	1392.6562	1392.6555	0.53	0	(60)	1.3e-06	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>5395</u>	697.3355	1392.6563	1392.6555	0.62	0	(53)	5.8e-06	1	U	Y.ICD

<u>5396</u>	697.3355	1392.6563	1392.6555	0.62	0	(39)	0.00014	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>5397</u>	697.3355	1392.6565	1392.6555	0.70	0	(58)	1.9e-06	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>5398</u>	697.3356	1392.6566	1392.6555	0.79	0	(50)	1.3e-05	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>5399</u>	465.2261	1392.6566	1392.6555	0.79	0	(52)	8.2e-06	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>5400</u>	465.2262	1392.6568	1392.6555	0.92	0	(35)	0.00037	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>5401</u>	697.3357	1392.6568	1392.6555	0.96	0	(51)	8.7e-06	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>5402</u>	697.3357	1392.6568	1392.6555	0.96	0	(63)	6.2e-07	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>5403</u>	697.3357	1392.6569	1392.6555	1.05	0	(58)	1.9e-06	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>5404</u>	697.3357	1392.6569	1392.6555	1.05	0	(65)	4e-07	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>5405</u>	697.3357	1392.6569	1392.6555	1.05	0	(58)	2e-06	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>5406</u>	697.3357	1392.6569	1392.6555	1.05	0	(59)	1.4e-06	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>5408</u>	697.3359	1392.6573	1392.6555	1.32	0	(59)	1.5e-06	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>5409</u>	697.3360	1392.6574	1392.6555	1.41	0	(28)	0.0019	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>5410</u>	697.3361	1392.6577	1392.6555	1.58	0	(73)	6e-08	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>5411</u>	697.3361	1392.6577	1392.6555	1.58	0	(37)	0.00025	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>5412</u>	697.3364	1392.6582	1392.6555	1.93	0	(60)	1.1e-06	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>5413</u>	697.3364	1392.6583	1392.6555	2.03	0	(61)	7.5e-07	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>5414</u>	697.3364	1392.6583	1392.6555	2.03	0	(69)	1.3e-07	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>5415</u>	697.3367	1392.6588	1392.6555	2.37	0	(48)	1.8e-05	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>5416</u>	697.3367	1392.6589	1392.6555	2.46	0	75	3.5e-08	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>5417</u>	697.3368	1392.6590	1392.6555	2.54	0	(61)	7.9e-07	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>5418</u>	697.3368	1392.6590	1392.6555	2.54	0	(28)	0.0018	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>5419</u>	697.3369	1392.6591	1392.6555	2.63	0	(74)	4.4e-08	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>5420</u>	697.3369	1392.6591	1392.6555	2.63	0	(60)	1.1e-06	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>5421</u>	697.3369	1392.6593	1392.6555	2.71	0	(66)	2.6e-07	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>5422</u>	697.3369	1392.6593	1392.6555	2.71	0	(41)	8.6e-05	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>5423</u>	697.3370	1392.6594	1392.6555	2.82	0	(49)	1.2e-05	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>5424</u>	697.3370	1392.6594	1392.6555	2.82	0	(53)	5.2e-06	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>5425</u>	697.3371	1392.6596	1392.6555	2.99	0	(52)	7.1e-06	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>5426</u>	697.3372	1392.6599	1392.6555	3.16	0	(56)	2.7e-06	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>5427</u>	697.3372	1392.6599	1392.6555	3.16	0	(56)	2.5e-06	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>5428</u>	697.3373	1392.6601	1392.6555	3.33	0	(69)	1.2e-07	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>5429</u>	697.3375	1392.6605	1392.6555	3.59	0	(65)	3e-07	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>5430</u>	697.3376	1392.6606	1392.6555	3.69	0	(46)	2.8e-05	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>5431</u>	697.3377	1392.6609	1392.6555	3.86	0	(69)	1.4e-07	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>5432</u>	697.3378	1392.6610	1392.6555	3.95	0	(68)	1.6e-07	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>5433</u>	697.3383	1392.6621	1392.6555	4.74	0	(64)	4.5e-07	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>5446</u>	697.8298	1393.6450	1393.6395	3.94	0	(65)	5.4e-07	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>5455</u>	698.3233	1394.6320	1394.6235	6.13	0	(33)	0.00079	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>5456</u>	698.3234	1394.6323	1394.6235	6.31	0	(38)	0.00024	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>5654</u>	711.4093	1420.8040	1420.8038	0.19	1	45	3.2e-05	1	U	L.LKH
<u>5657</u>	711.4111	1420.8076	1420.8038	2.69	1	(34)	0.00036	1	U	L.LKH
<u>6055</u>	736.9318	1471.8491	1471.8432	4.00	0	25	0.0031	1	U	L.LPK
<u>6285</u>	756.9351	1511.8557	1511.8559	-0.15	1	28	0.0015	1	U	F.AVE
<u>6286</u>	756.9365	1511.8585	1511.8559	1.70	1	(23)	0.0055	1	U	F.AVE
<u>6289</u>	757.3785	1512.7425	1512.7395	2.00	2	56	3e-06	1	U	Y.LQQ
<u>6290</u>	757.3790	1512.7435	1512.7395	2.65	2	(21)	0.01	1	U	Y.LQQ
<u>6291</u>	757.3791	1512.7436	1512.7395	2.73	2	(42)	8.1e-05	1	U	Y.LQQ
<u>6442</u>	769.8911	1537.7677	1537.7664	0.81	2	31	0.0014	1	U	F.SAL
<u>6443</u>	769.8934	1537.7722	1537.7664	3.75	2	(24)	0.0056	1	U	F.SAL
<u>6508</u>	774.9236	1547.8326	1547.8307	1.21	2	(40)	0.0001	1	U	F.DKL
<u>6509</u>	774.9253	1547.8361	1547.8307	3.50	2	44	3.8e-05	1	U	F.DKL
<u>6629</u>	784.8115	1567.6084	1567.6065	1.19	0	(52)	6.5e-06	1	U	F.QEC
<u>6630</u>	784.8117	1567.6089	1567.6065	1.51	0	(36)	0.00024	1	U	F.QEC
<u>6631</u>	784.8122	1567.6098	1567.6065	2.12	0	(30)	0.00091	1	U	F.QEC
<u>6632</u>	784.8123	1567.6100	1567.6065	2.21	0	(33)	0.00054	1	U	F.QEC
<u>6633</u>	784.8124	1567.6102	1567.6065	2.36	0	69	1.4e-07	1	U	F.QEC

<u>6635</u>	784.8129	1567.6112	1567.6065	2.99	0	(46)	2.6e-05	1	U	F.QEC
<u>6648</u>	785.2914	1568.5683	1568.5905	-14.14	0	(27)	0.0021	1	U	F.QEC
<u>6649</u>	785.2930	1568.5714	1568.5905	-12.19	0	(27)	0.0022	1	U	F.QEC
<u>6650</u>	785.3065	1568.5985	1568.5905	5.08	0	(41)	7.9e-05	1	U	F.QEC
<u>6651</u>	785.3072	1568.5998	1568.5905	5.94	0	(44)	4.2e-05	1	U	F.QEC
<u>6680</u>	525.2627	1572.7663	1572.7671	-0.55	2	(24)	0.0038	1	U	F.DEH
<u>6682</u>	787.3906	1572.7667	1572.7671	-0.27	2	48	1.6e-05	1	U	F.DEH
<u>6686</u>	787.3914	1572.7682	1572.7671	0.66	2	(39)	0.00012	1	U	F.DEH
<u>6688</u>	787.3923	1572.7701	1572.7671	1.89	2	(44)	4.1e-05	1	U	F.DEH
<u>6691</u>	787.3928	1572.7711	1572.7671	2.51	2	(37)	0.00019	1	U	F.DEH
<u>6757</u>	792.4536	1582.8927	1582.8930	-0.22	2	(21)	0.0082	1	U	F.AVE
<u>6776</u>	792.9460	1583.8775	1583.8770	0.32	2	31	0.00083	1	U	F.AVE
<u>6778</u>	792.9481	1583.8817	1583.8770	2.94	2	(29)	0.0012	1	U	F.AVE
<u>7209</u>	827.7986	1653.5827	1653.5858	-1.83	0	(44)	3.7e-05	1	U	L.EEC
<u>7211</u>	827.8022	1653.5898	1653.5858	2.45	0	61	7.4e-07	1	U	L.EEC
<u>7406</u>	563.5612	1687.6617	1687.6640	-1.41	0	(29)	0.0012	1	U	F.VDK
<u>7407</u>	563.5613	1687.6620	1687.6640	-1.20	0	(36)	0.00025	1	U	F.VDK
<u>7408</u>	563.5614	1687.6624	1687.6640	-0.98	0	(22)	0.0067	1	U	F.VDK
<u>7409</u>	844.8387	1687.6628	1687.6640	-0.73	0	(53)	5e-06	1	U	F.VDK
<u>7410</u>	563.5617	1687.6633	1687.6640	-0.43	0	(31)	0.00078	1	U	F.VDK
<u>7411</u>	563.5623	1687.6650	1687.6640	0.55	0	(37)	0.00021	1	U	F.VDK
<u>7412</u>	563.5623	1687.6650	1687.6640	0.55	0	(28)	0.0017	1	U	F.VDK
<u>7413</u>	844.8398	1687.6651	1687.6640	0.65	0	61	7.4e-07	1	U	F.VDK
<u>7414</u>	563.5623	1687.6651	1687.6640	0.65	0	(43)	4.6e-05	1	U	F.VDK
<u>7416</u>	844.8405	1687.6665	1687.6640	1.46	0	(40)	0.0001	1	U	F.VDK
<u>7417</u>	844.8407	1687.6668	1687.6640	1.67	0	(58)	1.7e-06	1	U	F.VDK
<u>7418</u>	844.8407	1687.6668	1687.6640	1.67	0	(47)	1.8e-05	1	U	F.VDK
<u>7419</u>	844.8409	1687.6672	1687.6640	1.88	0	(52)	6.6e-06	1	U	F.VDK
<u>7887</u>	886.4197	1770.8249	1770.8247	0.15	2	(36)	0.00042	1	U	L.IKQ
<u>7888</u>	591.2823	1770.8252	1770.8247	0.32	2	(43)	8.7e-05	1	U	L.IKQ
<u>7889</u>	591.2825	1770.8258	1770.8247	0.62	2	52	1.1e-05	1	U	L.IKQ
<u>7890</u>	886.4221	1770.8297	1770.8247	2.84	2	(34)	0.00073	1	U	L.IKQ
<u>8149</u>	931.9223	1861.8300	1861.8298	0.11	0	53	1.7e-05	1	U	F.AKT
<u>8151</u>	621.6177	1861.8314	1861.8298	0.84	0	(31)	0.0025	1	U	F.AKT
<u>8153</u>	621.6196	1861.8371	1861.8298	3.88	0	(36)	0.00081	1	U	F.AKT
<u>8492</u>	662.6098	1984.8076	1984.8077	-0.08	1	(31)	0.0018	1	U	Y.NGV
<u>8493</u>	993.4123	1984.8101	1984.8077	1.21	1	(60)	2.2e-06	1	U	Y.NGV
<u>8494</u>	662.6110	1984.8112	1984.8077	1.76	1	(31)	0.0016	1	U	Y.NGV
<u>8495</u>	993.4143	1984.8141	1984.8077	3.19	1	(66)	4.6e-07	1	U	Y.NGV
<u>8497</u>	993.9052	1985.7959	1985.7917	2.07	1	(63)	9.2e-07	1	U	Y.NGV
<u>8499</u>	993.9061	1985.7976	1985.7917	2.94	1	(62)	1.4e-06	1	U	Y.NGV
<u>8502</u>	663.2641	1986.7705	1986.7758	-2.66	1	(24)	0.0068	1	U	Y.NGV
<u>8503</u>	994.3939	1986.7733	1986.7758	-1.24	1	67	3.3e-07	1	U	Y.NGV
<u>8504</u>	663.2673	1986.7800	1986.7758	2.13	1	(42)	0.00012	1	U	Y.NGV
<u>8505</u>	994.3975	1986.7804	1986.7758	2.32	1	(65)	5.4e-07	1	U	Y.NGV
<u>8667</u>	1016.4501	2030.8856	2030.8891	-1.73	1	(40)	0.00034	1	U	F.AED
<u>8668</u>	1016.4520	2030.8895	2030.8891	0.20	1	47	6.3e-05	1	U	F.AED
<u>8670</u>	508.7301	2030.8913	2030.8891	1.08	1	(24)	0.015	1	U	F.AED
<u>8779</u>	1034.9066	2067.7987	2067.7972	0.71	1	56	2.7e-06	1	U	Y.EAT
<u>8781</u>	1034.9070	2067.7994	2067.7972	1.06	1	(35)	0.00035	1	U	Y.EAT
<u>8782</u>	690.2738	2067.7996	2067.7972	1.14	1	(26)	0.0024	1	U	Y.EAT
<u>8783</u>	690.2742	2067.8009	2067.7972	1.77	1	(23)	0.0046	1	U	Y.EAT
<u>8786</u>	1034.9084	2067.8023	2067.7972	2.48	1	(52)	5.8e-06	1	U	Y.EAT
<u>8787</u>	1034.9087	2067.8028	2067.7972	2.72	1	(40)	9.5e-05	1	U	Y.EAT
<u>8789</u>	690.2750	2067.8032	2067.7972	2.91	1	(22)	0.0069	1	U	Y.EAT
<u>8953</u>	530.0270	2116.0791	2116.0800	-0.46	1	(25)	0.0034	1	U	L.SHK
<u>8956</u>	1059.0475	2116.0804	2116.0800	0.19	1	(65)	4e-07	1	U	L.SHK

8959	530.0277	2116.0817	2116.0800	0.81	1	(35)	0.00034	1	U	L.SHK
8960	1059.0483	2116.0821	2116.0800	0.99	1	(46)	2.6e-05	1	U	L.SHK
8961	706.3680	2116.0823	2116.0800	1.07	1	(38)	0.00017	1	U	L.SHK
8962	706.3682	2116.0827	2116.0800	1.24	1	(24)	0.0048	1	U	L.SHK
8965	530.0280	2116.0830	2116.0800	1.39	1	(22)	0.0072	1	U	L.SHK
8966	530.0281	2116.0835	2116.0800	1.62	1	(32)	0.00071	1	U	L.SHK
8968	530.0282	2116.0837	2116.0800	1.73	1	(21)	0.0086	1	U	L.SHK
8969	530.0282	2116.0837	2116.0800	1.73	1	(29)	0.0015	1	U	L.SHK
8974	706.3692	2116.0858	2116.0800	2.71	1	(36)	0.00028	1	U	L.SHK
8977	1059.0515	2116.0885	2116.0800	3.99	1	69	1.6e-07	1	U	L.SHK
9031	711.6826	2132.0259	2132.0242	0.78	0	27	0.0041	1	U	L.HEK
9250	744.0613	2229.1622	2229.1641	-0.85	2	(22)	0.0059	1	U	F.LSH
9259	558.2985	2229.1650	2229.1641	0.40	2	(22)	0.0065	1	U	F.LSH
9262	1115.5900	2229.1654	2229.1641	0.58	2	51	7.8e-06	1	U	F.LSH
9265	558.2988	2229.1662	2229.1641	0.95	2	(21)	0.0072	1	U	F.LSH
9266	558.2989	2229.1665	2229.1641	1.06	2	(21)	0.0084	1	U	F.LSH
9267	1115.5907	2229.1668	2229.1641	1.24	2	(51)	7.8e-06	1	U	F.LSH
9273	744.0640	2229.1703	2229.1641	2.77	2	(43)	5.4e-05	1	U	F.LSH
9276	744.0651	2229.1734	2229.1641	4.15	2	(30)	0.00093	1	U	F.LSH
9278	1115.5990	2229.1834	2229.1641	8.68	2	(43)	4.8e-05	1	U	F.LSH
9333	758.9542	2273.8408	2273.8446	-1.65	0	(28)	0.0015	1	U	Y.GDM
9334	1137.9282	2273.8419	2273.8446	-1.18	0	(28)	0.0018	1	U	Y.GDM
9335	1137.9294	2273.8443	2273.8446	-0.11	0	(25)	0.0035	1	U	Y.GDM
9336	758.9570	2273.8491	2273.8446	1.98	0	(31)	0.00074	1	U	Y.GDM
9337	758.9574	2273.8504	2273.8446	2.55	0	(29)	0.0014	1	U	Y.GDM
9338	758.9575	2273.8507	2273.8446	2.71	0	(29)	0.0013	1	U	Y.GDM
9339	1137.9343	2273.8541	2273.8446	4.19	0	(38)	0.00017	1	U	Y.GDM
9341	759.2892	2274.8457	2274.8286	7.53	0	(35)	0.0003	1	U	Y.GDM
9374	764.2872	2289.8399	2289.8395	0.16	0	41	7.9e-05	1	U	Y.GDM
9375	764.2877	2289.8413	2289.8395	0.80	0	(30)	0.0009	1	U	Y.GDM
9376	1145.9290	2289.8434	2289.8395	1.69	0	(29)	0.0012	1	U	Y.GDM
9377	764.2890	2289.8452	2289.8395	2.48	0	(23)	0.0054	1	U	Y.GDM
9378	1145.9302	2289.8458	2289.8395	2.76	0	(21)	0.0083	1	U	Y.GDM
9662	1194.4729	2386.9312	2386.9286	1.09	1	(20)	0.013	1	U	Y.GDM
9664	1194.4758	2386.9371	2386.9286	3.55	1	(24)	0.006	1	U	Y.GDM
9665	1194.4762	2386.9378	2386.9286	3.86	1	(25)	0.005	1	U	Y.GDM
9666	796.6537	2386.9394	2386.9286	4.52	1	(21)	0.011	1	U	Y.GDM
9668	796.9842	2387.9307	2387.9126	7.58	1	(22)	0.0062	1	U	Y.GDM
9701	801.9824	2402.9253	2402.9236	0.71	1	30	0.0014	1	U	Y.GDM
9705	803.0491	2406.1254	2406.1447	-8.02	2	(28)	0.0062	1	U	F.LSH
9858	1334.6290	2667.2435	2667.2486	-1.92	2	46	7.5e-05	1	U	L.SHK
9861	890.0911	2667.2516	2667.2486	1.09	2	(31)	0.0023	1	U	L.SHK
9868	890.0922	2667.2547	2667.2486	2.25	2	(25)	0.0095	1	U	L.SHK
9869	1334.6350	2667.2555	2667.2486	2.56	2	(33)	0.0015	1	U	L.SHK
9871	890.4200	2668.2383	2668.2327	2.11	2	(39)	0.00045	1	U	L.SHK
9872	890.4202	2668.2389	2668.2327	2.33	2	(26)	0.0095	1	U	L.SHK
9990	941.8029	2822.3869	2822.3796	2.59	1	25	0.0035	1	U	L.EKS
10025	971.1520	2910.4343	2910.3779	19.4	1	(23)	0.0072	1	U	L.EKS
10027	971.1534	2910.4385	2910.3779	20.8	1	(24)	0.0055	1	U	L.EKS
10038	979.4963	2935.4672	2935.4637	1.20	2	59	1.5e-06	1	U	L.LEK
10039	979.4969	2935.4688	2935.4637	1.76	2	(25)	0.0039	1	U	L.LEK

2.

[1::sp|cRAP002|P02768|ALBU_HUMAN](#)

Mass: 71317

Score: 306

Matches: 63 (63)

Seq

Serum albumin OS=Homo sapiens GN=ALB PE=1 SV=2

Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptid
256	396.6888	791.3630	791.3636	-0.77	1	(23)	0.0056	1		Y.LQQC
260	396.6890	791.3635	791.3636	-0.14	1	24	0.0043	1		Y.LQQC
2417	521.2842	1040.5538	1040.5515	2.19	0	25	0.0032	1		Y.EIAR
2530	526.7459	1051.4771	1051.5008	-22.50	1	21	0.013	2	U	L.IKQN
2616	532.2496	1062.4846	1062.4838	0.76	0	35	0.00029	1	U	L.KECC
2621	532.7172	1063.4198	1063.4240	-4.00	0	(22)	0.0058	1		L.ECAD
2623	532.7201	1063.4256	1063.4240	1.51	0	(39)	0.00011	1		L.ECAD
2625	532.7202	1063.4259	1063.4240	1.73	0	43	4.7e-05	1		L.ECAD
2627	532.7210	1063.4273	1063.4240	3.12	0	(28)	0.0015	1		L.ECAD
2982	555.2849	1108.5553	1108.5665	-10.16	0	(22)	0.0063	1	U	L.SQRF
2983	555.2850	1108.5554	1108.5665	-10.05	0	24	0.0039	1	U	L.SQRF
3523	589.2612	1176.5078	1176.5081	-0.25	1	(40)	0.00011	1		L.LECA
3526	589.2626	1176.5106	1176.5081	2.13	1	45	3e-05	1		L.LECA
5375	697.3327	1392.6508	1392.6555	-3.32	0	(28)	0.0016	2	U	Y.ICEN
5377	697.3334	1392.6522	1392.6555	-2.36	0	(20)	0.01	2	U	Y.ICEN
5378	697.3334	1392.6522	1392.6555	-2.36	0	(30)	0.001	2	U	Y.ICEN
5379	697.3334	1392.6523	1392.6555	-2.26	0	(29)	0.0014	2	U	Y.ICEN
5380	697.3345	1392.6544	1392.6555	-0.78	0	(30)	0.0011	2	U	Y.ICEN
5381	697.3345	1392.6545	1392.6555	-0.69	0	(33)	0.00064	2	U	Y.ICEN
5383	697.3348	1392.6551	1392.6555	-0.25	0	(27)	0.0024	2	U	Y.ICEN
5384	697.3349	1392.6552	1392.6555	-0.16	0	(22)	0.0068	2	U	Y.ICEN
5385	697.3350	1392.6554	1392.6555	-0.07	0	(28)	0.0017	2	U	Y.ICEN
5386	697.3350	1392.6555	1392.6555	0.01	0	(31)	0.00093	2	U	Y.ICEN
5387	697.3351	1392.6556	1392.6555	0.10	0	(31)	0.00095	2	U	Y.ICEN
5388	697.3351	1392.6556	1392.6555	0.10	0	(30)	0.0012	2	U	Y.ICEN
5389	697.3351	1392.6557	1392.6555	0.18	0	38	0.00017	2	U	Y.ICEN
5390	697.3351	1392.6557	1392.6555	0.18	0	(33)	0.00065	2	U	Y.ICEN
5392	697.3352	1392.6559	1392.6555	0.28	0	(33)	0.00067	2	U	Y.ICEN
5393	697.3354	1392.6562	1392.6555	0.54	0	(26)	0.0029	2	U	Y.ICEN
5395	697.3355	1392.6563	1392.6555	0.63	0	(33)	0.00055	2	U	Y.ICEN
5397	697.3355	1392.6565	1392.6555	0.72	0	(30)	0.0011	2	U	Y.ICEN
5398	697.3356	1392.6566	1392.6555	0.80	0	(21)	0.011	2	U	Y.ICEN
5399	465.2261	1392.6566	1392.6555	0.80	0	(21)	0.0094	2	U	Y.ICEN
5401	697.3357	1392.6568	1392.6555	0.97	0	(20)	0.011	2	U	Y.ICEN
5402	697.3357	1392.6568	1392.6555	0.97	0	(31)	0.0009	2	U	Y.ICEN
5403	697.3357	1392.6569	1392.6555	1.06	0	(25)	0.0041	2	U	Y.ICEN
5404	697.3357	1392.6569	1392.6555	1.06	0	(22)	0.0082	2	U	Y.ICEN
5405	697.3357	1392.6569	1392.6555	1.06	0	(27)	0.0026	2	U	Y.ICEN
5406	697.3357	1392.6569	1392.6555	1.06	0	(22)	0.0068	2	U	Y.ICEN
5408	697.3359	1392.6573	1392.6555	1.33	0	(28)	0.002	2	U	Y.ICEN
5410	697.3361	1392.6577	1392.6555	1.59	0	(37)	0.00026	2	U	Y.ICEN
5412	697.3364	1392.6582	1392.6555	1.94	0	(29)	0.0015	2	U	Y.ICEN
5413	697.3364	1392.6583	1392.6555	2.04	0	(23)	0.0056	2	U	Y.ICEN
5414	697.3364	1392.6583	1392.6555	2.04	0	(33)	0.00057	2	U	Y.ICEN
5415	697.3367	1392.6588	1392.6555	2.38	0	(22)	0.0074	2	U	Y.ICEN

5416	697.3367	1392.6589	1392.6555	2.47	0	(28)	0.0015	2	U	Y.ICEN
5417	697.3368	1392.6590	1392.6555	2.55	0	(25)	0.0033	2	U	Y.ICEN
5419	697.3369	1392.6591	1392.6555	2.64	0	(32)	0.00067	2	U	Y.ICEN
5420	697.3369	1392.6591	1392.6555	2.64	0	(30)	0.0012	2	U	Y.ICEN
5421	697.3369	1392.6593	1392.6555	2.73	0	(26)	0.0024	2	U	Y.ICEN
5424	697.3370	1392.6594	1392.6555	2.83	0	(25)	0.0035	2	U	Y.ICEN
5425	697.3371	1392.6596	1392.6555	3.00	0	(34)	0.00042	2	U	Y.ICEN
5426	697.3372	1392.6599	1392.6555	3.17	0	(21)	0.0077	2	U	Y.ICEN
5427	697.3372	1392.6599	1392.6555	3.17	0	(24)	0.0047	2	U	Y.ICEN
5428	697.3373	1392.6601	1392.6555	3.34	0	(29)	0.0013	2	U	Y.ICEN
5429	697.3375	1392.6605	1392.6555	3.60	0	(30)	0.0012	2	U	Y.ICEN
5430	697.3376	1392.6606	1392.6555	3.70	0	(23)	0.0059	2	U	Y.ICEN
5431	697.3377	1392.6609	1392.6555	3.87	0	(31)	0.00076	2	U	Y.ICEN
5432	697.3378	1392.6610	1392.6555	3.96	0	(32)	0.0006	2	U	Y.ICEN
5433	697.3383	1392.6621	1392.6555	4.75	0	(30)	0.0011	2	U	Y.ICEN
5446	697.8298	1393.6450	1393.6395	3.95	0	(23)	0.0087	3	U	Y.ICEN
6289	757.3785	1512.7425	1512.7395	2.00	2	52	7.8e-06	2	U	Y.LQQC
6291	757.3791	1512.7436	1512.7395	2.73	2	(29)	0.0014	2	U	Y.LQQC

3. [1::sp|cRAP022|P00766|CTRA_BOVIN](#) **Mass:** 26220 **Score:** 140 **Matches:** 8(8) **Seque**
 Chymotrypsinogen A OS=Bos taurus PE=1 SV=1
 Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
552	412.7285	823.4424	823.4440	-1.85	1	35	0.0003	1	U	L.KLSTA
553	412.7285	823.4425	823.4440	-1.78	1	(25)	0.0033	1	U	L.KLSTA
2063	501.2540	1000.4934	1000.4938	-0.31	0	25	0.0029	1	U	Y.TNANT
2064	501.2541	1000.4936	1000.4938	-0.13	0	(24)	0.0036	1	U	Y.TNANT
2221	508.7844	1015.5543	1015.5550	-0.66	1	(31)	0.00075	1	U	L.TINND
2222	508.7845	1015.5544	1015.5550	-0.55	1	34	0.00043	1	U	L.TINND
3263	575.2542	1148.4939	1148.4921	1.58	1	23	0.0049	1	U	F.CGGSL
7920	892.4402	1782.8658	1782.8689	-1.74	0	23	0.013	1	U	L.SRIVN

4. [1::sp|cRAP112|P00761|TRYP_PIG](#) **Mass:** 25078 **Score:** 60 **Matches:** 5(5) **Sequenc**
 Trypsin OS=Sus scrofa PE=1 SV=1
 Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
877	429.7375	857.4605	857.4607	-0.13	0	(25)	0.0034	1	U	W.IQQT
878	429.7376	857.4606	857.4607	-0.06	0	28	0.0015	1	U	W.IQQT
4408	629.3331	1256.6517	1256.6513	0.31	1	(27)	0.0019	1	U	Y.VNWIQ
4409	629.3338	1256.6530	1256.6513	1.37	1	32	0.00066	1	U	Y.VNWIQ
4422	629.8281	1257.6416	1257.6353	4.96	1	(21)	0.0071	1	U	Y.VNWIQ

5. [1::sp|cRAP091|Q10735|PEPB_PIG](#) **Mass:** 7794 **Score:** 25 **Matches:** 1(1) **Sequenc**
 Pepsin B (Fragment) OS=Sus scrofa GN=PGB PE=1 SV=1
 Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
130	387.7330	773.4515	773.4469	5.94	0	25	0.0032	1	U	-.MERIIL.R

6. [1::sp|cRAP015|P02666|CASB BOVIN](#) Mass: 25148 Score: 25 Matches: 3(3) Sequen

Beta-casein OS=Bos taurus GN=CSN2 PE=1 SV=2
Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
830	426.7283	851.4420	851.4496	-8.91	1	27	0.0019	1	U	-.MKVLIL.A
833	426.7287	851.4428	851.4496	-7.97	1	(21)	0.0086	1	U	-.MKVLIL.A
835	426.7288	851.4430	851.4496	-7.76	1	(25)	0.0034	1	U	-.MKVLIL.A

7. [1::sp|cRAP008|P00722|BGAL ECOLI](#) Mass: 117321 Score: 22 Matches: 1(1) Sequen

Beta-galactosidase OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) GN=lacZ PE=1 SV=2
Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
1107	448.2306	894.4466	894.4269	22.0	1	22	0.0063	1	U	L.LMKQNF.

8. [1::sp|cRAP004|P04745|AMY1 HUMAN](#) Mass: 58415 Score: 22 Matches: 2(2) Sequen

Alpha-amylase 1 OS=Homo sapiens GN=AMY1A PE=1 SV=2
Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
1027	440.2266	878.4386	878.4246	15.9	0	(22)	0.0067	1	U	F.GNGRVTEF
1028	440.2267	878.4389	878.4246	16.3	0	22	0.0066	1	U	F.GNGRVTEF

9. [1::sp|cRAP020|P01031|CO5 HUMAN](#) Mass: 189897 Score: 21 Matches: 1(1) Sequen

Complement C5 OS=Homo sapiens GN=C5 PE=1 SV=4
Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
763	424.2261	846.4376	846.4521	-17.02	0	23	0.0048	1	U	L.IEKQKL.

Search Parameters

Type of search : MS/MS Ion Search
 Enzyme : Chymotrypsin
 Fixed modifications : [Carbamidomethyl \(C\)](#)
 Variable modifications : [Deamidated \(NQ\)](#), [DTSSP Cross link \(K\)](#), [DTSSP Cross link di oxidation \(K\)](#), [DTSSP Cross link single oxidation \(K\)](#), [DTSSP Cross link tri oxidation \(K\)](#), [Oxidation \(M\)](#)

Mass values : Monoisotopic
Protein Mass : Unrestricted
Peptide Mass Tolerance : $\pm$ 25 ppm
Fragment Mass Tolerance: $\pm$ 0.8 Da
Max Missed Cleavages : 2
Instrument type : ESI-TRAP
Number of queries : 10169

Mascot: <http://www.matrixscience.com/>